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public class EmployeeDirectory {
    private Map<String, String> employees;

    public EmployeeDirectory() {
        employees = new HashMap<>();
    }

    public boolean addEmployee(String id, String name) {
        if (employees.containsKey(id)) {
            return false;
        }
        employees.put(id, name);
        return true;
    }

    public String removeEmployee(String id) {
        return employees.remove(id);
    }

    public void printDirectory() {
        for (String id : employees.keySet()) {
            System.out.println("ID: " + id + ", Name: " + employees.get(id));
        }
    }

    public static void main(String[] args) {
        EmployeeDirectory dir = new EmployeeDirectory();

        boolean r1 = dir.addEmployee("E001", "Alice");
        boolean r2 = dir.addEmployee("E001", "Bob");
        boolean r3 = dir.addEmployee("E002", "Alice");

        System.out.print("Results: " + r1 + ", " + r2 + ", " + r3 + " | ");
        dir.printDirectory();
    }
}
```